

<p>Kia launches (unidiomatic style; MINOR) the (grammar; NEUTRAL) new Kia Flex (grammar; NEUTRAL) subscription program (punctuation; MINOR) where you can rent your car from (grammar; NEUTRAL) 6 (inconsistent with external reference; NEUTRAL) months (awkward style; NEUTRAL) to 24 months, whether it is electric or combustion, (punctuation; MINOR) a (capitalisation; MINOR) 100% digital process where you can see if (grammar; NEUTRAL) you are automatically approved to take (grammar; NEUTRAL) this (grammar; MINOR) car, (punctuation; MINOR) or not (grammar; NEUTRAL) and you can have it within a period of (unidiomatic style; MINOR) one or two weeks at the latest, (punctuation; MINOR) including (substitution; MINOR) what (punctuation; MINOR) (deletion; MINOR) is included, (punctuation; MINOR) all (substitution; MINOR) (punctuation; MINOR) maintenance (capitalisation; MINOR), breakdowns, roadside assistance (textual conventions; MINOR). With this program (punctuation; NEUTRAL) we are (language register; NEUTRAL) running out of (deletion; MINOR) opportunities (addition; MINOR) to not (grammar; MINOR) have a Kia vehicle and these new mobility services. [Music] (insertion; NEUTRAL) (deletion; MINOR)</p>	<p>unidiomatic style; MINOR</p>	<p>unidiomatic style; MINOR</p>	<p>2</p>
	grammar; NEUTRAL	grammar; NEUTRAL	6
	grammar; NEUTRAL	punctuation; MINOR	7
	punctuation; MINOR	inconsistent with external reference; NEUTRAL	1
	grammar; NEUTRAL	awkward style; NEUTRAL	1
	inconsistent with external reference; NEUTRAL	capitalisation; MINOR	2
	awkward style; NEUTRAL	grammar; MINOR	2
	punctuation; MINOR	substitution; MINOR	2
	capitalisation; MINOR	deletion; MINOR	3
	grammar; NEUTRAL	textual conventions; MINOR	1
	grammar; NEUTRAL	punctuation; NEUTRAL	1
	grammar; MINOR	language register; NEUTRAL	1
	punctuation; MINOR	addition; MINOR	1
	grammar; NEUTRAL	insertion; NEUTRAL	1
	unidiomatic style; MINOR		
	punctuation; MINOR		
	substitution; MINOR		
	punctuation; MINOR		
	deletion; MINOR		
	punctuation; MINOR		
	substitution; MINOR		
	punctuation; MINOR		
	capitalisation; MINOR		
	textual conventions; MINOR		
	punctuation; NEUTRAL		
	language register; NEUTRAL		
	deletion; MINOR		
	addition; MINOR		
	grammar; MINOR		

	insertion; NEUTRAL		
	deletion; MINOR		

<p>[Music] (insertion; NEUTRAL) Here we have our new iv3 (substitution; MAJOR), which (punctuation; MINOR) in line with our electrics (textual conventions; NEUTRAL) (punctuation; MINOR) has the 10 essential materials from Kia (unidiomatic style; MINOR) (punctuation; NEUTRAL) in our commitment to be more sustainable and also (awkward style; NEUTRAL) take care of the environment. They have a two-tone upholstery made of vegan leather. They also have (unidiomatic style; MINOR) recycled elements of PET, which is the most recyclable plastic in the world. This material is also in the headliner and the doors (mistranslation; MINOR) (punctuation; NEUTRAL) in line (grammar; NEUTRAL) with Kia's 10 essential materials. The seats are very comfortable. You can adjust them to suit you best (grammar; NEUTRAL). You also have two memory positions (punctuation; NEUTRAL) in case you have to exchange the car (language register; MINOR) with someone else (punctuation; NEUTRAL) and the option of having both heated and ventilated seats to adapt to any weather situation. [Music] (insertion; NEUTRAL) (deletion; MINOR)</p>	<p>insertion; NEUTRAL</p>		
	<p>insertion; NEUTRAL</p>	<p>insertion; NEUTRAL</p>	<p>2</p>
	<p>substitution; MAJOR</p>	<p>substitution; MAJOR</p>	<p>1</p>
	<p>punctuation; MINOR</p>	<p>punctuation; MINOR</p>	<p>2</p>
	<p>textual conventions; NEUTRAL</p>	<p>textual conventions; NEUTRAL</p>	<p>1</p>
	<p>punctuation; MINOR</p>	<p>unidiomatic style; MINOR</p>	<p>2</p>
	<p>unidiomatic style; MINOR</p>	<p>punctuation; NEUTRAL</p>	<p>4</p>
	<p>punctuation; NEUTRAL</p>	<p>awkward style; NEUTRAL</p>	<p>1</p>
	<p>awkward style; NEUTRAL</p>	<p>mistranslation; MINOR</p>	<p>1</p>
	<p>unidiomatic style; MINOR</p>	<p>grammar; NEUTRAL</p>	<p>2</p>
	<p>mistranslation; MINOR</p>	<p>language register; MINOR</p>	<p>1</p>
	<p>punctuation; NEUTRAL</p>	<p>deletion; MINOR</p>	<p>1</p>
	<p>grammar; NEUTRAL</p>		
	<p>grammar; NEUTRAL</p>		
	<p>punctuation; NEUTRAL</p>		
	<p>language register; MINOR</p>		
	<p>punctuation; NEUTRAL</p>		
	<p>insertion; NEUTRAL</p>		
	<p>deletion; MINOR</p>		

<p>[Music] (insertion; NEUTRAL) the (capitalisation; MINOR) trunk of the elb 3 (substitution; MAJOR) is one of the largest in its segment with 460 l (inconsistent with external reference; NEUTRAL) of capacity (awkward style; NEUTRAL) (punctuation; MINOR)(capitalisation; MINOR) apart from that (punctuation; NEUTRAL) it has a double bottom (punctuation; NEUTRAL) so we can have (grammar; NEUTRAL) the tray up and use the compartment below to store the (grammar; NEUTRAL) charging cables (punctuation; MINOR) and if you need more [Music] (insertion; MINOR) space (punctuation; NEUTRAL) you lower it and you have all this extra space available (punctuation; MINOR) (capitalisation; MINOR) it is (language register; NEUTRAL) not only the trunk (awkward style; MINOR) but also the interior space (grammar; NEUTRAL) (punctuation; MINOR) (capitalisation; MINOR) the rear seats allow three occupants to travel with maximum comfort (punctuation; NEUTRAL) and the front space (punctuation; MINOR)with its sliding tray (punctuation; MINOR) offers extra comfort to drivers (punctuation; MINOR) And finally mention (textual conventions; MINOR) (punctuation; NEUTRAL) this car also has a Frank (substitution; MINOR) (punctuation; NEUTRAL)or front trunk(punctuation; NEUTRAL) of (grammar; NEUTRAL) up to 25 l (inconsistent with external reference; NEUTRAL) (grammar; MINOR) capacity to house (awkward style; NEUTRAL) (punctuation; NEUTRAL) for example (punctuation; NEUTRAL) a charging cable (punctuation; MINOR) [Music] (insertion; NEUTRAL)(deletion; MINOR)</p>	<p>insertion; NEUTRAL</p>	<p>insertion; NEUTRAL</p>	<p>2</p>
	<p>capitalisation; MINOR</p>	<p>capitalisation; MINOR</p>	<p>4</p>
	<p>substitution; MAJOR</p>	<p>substitution; MAJOR</p>	<p>1</p>
	<p>inconsistent with external reference; NEUTRAL</p>	<p>inconsistent with external reference; NEUTRAL</p>	<p>2</p>
	<p>awkward style; NEUTRAL</p>	<p>awkward style; NEUTRAL</p>	<p>2</p>
	<p>punctuation; MINOR</p>	<p>punctuation; MINOR</p>	<p>8</p>
	<p>capitalisation; MINOR</p>	<p>punctuation; NEUTRAL</p>	<p>9</p>
	<p>punctuation; NEUTRAL</p>	<p>grammar; NEUTRAL</p>	<p>4</p>
	<p>punctuation; NEUTRAL</p>	<p>insertion; MINOR</p>	<p>1</p>
	<p>grammar; NEUTRAL</p>	<p>language register; NEUTRAL</p>	<p>1</p>
	<p>grammar; NEUTRAL</p>	<p>awkward style; MINOR</p>	<p>1</p>
	<p>punctuation; MINOR</p>	<p>textual conventions; MINOR</p>	<p>1</p>
	<p>insertion; MINOR</p>	<p>substitution; MINOR</p>	<p>1</p>
	<p>punctuation; NEUTRAL</p>	<p>grammar; MINOR</p>	<p>1</p>
	<p>punctuation; MINOR</p>	<p>deletion; MINOR</p>	<p>1</p>
	<p>capitalisation; MINOR</p>		
	<p>language register; NEUTRAL</p>		
	<p>awkward style; MINOR</p>		
	<p>grammar; NEUTRAL</p>		
	<p>punctuation; MINOR</p>		
	<p>capitalisation; MINOR</p>		
	<p>punctuation; NEUTRAL</p>		
	<p>punctuation; MINOR</p>		
	<p>punctuation; MINOR</p>		
	<p>punctuation; MINOR</p>		
	<p>textual conventions; MINOR</p>		

	punctuation; NEUTRAL		
	substitution; MINOR		
	punctuation; NEUTRAL		
	punctuation; NEUTRAL		
	grammar; NEUTRAL		
	inconsistent with external reference; NEUTRAL		
	grammar; MINOR		
	awkward style; NEUTRAL		
	punctuation; NEUTRAL		
	punctuation; NEUTRAL		
	punctuation; MINOR		
	insertion; NEUTRAL		
	deletion; MINOR		

<p>How your driving affects the autonomy (wrong term; MAJOR) of the electric vehicle (grammar; MINOR) (punctuation; MINOR) as it happens (unidiomatic style; NEUTRAL) with combustion vehicles (punctuation; MINOR) if you have an energetic drive (textual conventions; MINOR) it will decrease, (punctuation; NEUTRAL) on the contrary (punctuation; MINOR) if you drive efficiently (punctuation; NEUTRAL) the autonomy (wrong term; MAJOR) will increase (punctuation; MINOR) (capitalisation; MINOR) for more detailed information (punctuation; NEUTRAL) you can use (grammar; MINOR) the central screen (inconsistent with terminology resource; MINOR) (punctuation; MINOR) (capitalisation; MINOR) in it (grammar; MINOR) (punctuation; NEUTRAL) you will be able to (awkward style; NEUTRAL) see the total autonomy (wrong term; MAJOR) (punctuation; MINOR) in this case (punctuation; NEUTRAL) 377 km (punctuation; MINOR) (capitalisation; MINOR) we have traveled 782 km (capitalisation; MINOR) And we have an average consumption of 16.9 kw (inconsistent with external reference; NEUTRAL) at 100 kw (mistranslation; MINOR) (punctuation; MINOR) (capitalisation; MINOR) finally in the lower central space (punctuation; NEUTRAL) we will be able to (awkward style; NEUTRAL) see the instantaneous consumption bar (inconsistent with terminology resource; MINOR) (punctuation; MINOR) (capitalisation; MINOR) in (grammar; MINOR) it will show us (punctuation; NEUTRAL) in a very graphic way (unidiomatic style; MINOR) (punctuation; MINOR)the consumption that (grammar; NEUTRAL) we make by both pressing (grammar; NEUTRAL) the accelerator more or less (textual conventions; MINOR) (punctuation; MINOR) if we have air conditioning (grammar; MINOR) (punctuation; MINOR) if we are going up a mountain (punctuation; MINOR) it will give (grammar; MINOR) us a super clear idea of how much we are consuming (punctuation; MINOR) (capitalisation; MINOR) the Kia infotainment system (awkward style; NEUTRAL) will allow you to reflect (grammar; MINOR) the (grammar; MINOR) consumption data from the point that (grammar; NEUTRAL) you determine (capitalisation; MINOR) When starting the trip (grammar; MINOR) (punctuation; MINOR) since the last recharge (punctuation; MINOR)or since you bought the vehicle (punctuation; MINOR)[Music] (insertion; NEUTRAL) (deletion; MINOR)</p>	<p>wrong term; MAJOR</p>		
	wrong term; MAJOR	wrong term; MAJOR	3
	grammar; MINOR	grammar; MINOR	9
	punctuation; MINOR	punctuation; MINOR	17
	unidiomatic style; NEUTRAL	unidiomatic style; NEUTRAL	1
	punctuation; MINOR	textual conventions; MINOR	2
	textual conventions; MINOR	punctuation; NEUTRAL	7
	punctuation; NEUTRAL	capitalisation; MINOR	8
	punctuation; MINOR	inconsistent with terminology reso	2
	punctuation; NEUTRAL	awkward style; NEUTRAL	3
	wrong term; MAJOR	inconsistent with external referenc	1
	punctuation; MINOR	mistranslation; MINOR	1
	capitalisation; MINOR	unidiomatic style; MINOR	1
	punctuation; NEUTRAL	grammar; NEUTRAL	3
	grammar; MINOR	insertion; NEUTRAL	1
	inconsistent with terminology resource; MINOR	deletion; MINOR	1
	punctuation; MINOR		
	capitalisation; MINOR		
	grammar; MINOR		
	punctuation; NEUTRAL		
	awkward style; NEUTRAL		
	wrong term; MAJOR		
	punctuation; MINOR		
	punctuation; NEUTRAL		

	punctuation; MINOR		
	capitalisation; MINOR		
	capitalisation; MINOR		
	inconsistent with external reference; NEUTRAL		
	mistranslation; MINOR		
	punctuation; MINOR		
	capitalisation; MINOR		
	punctuation; NEUTRAL		
	awkward style; NEUTRAL		
	inconsistent with terminology resource; MINOR		
	punctuation; MINOR		
	capitalisation; MINOR		
	grammar; MINOR		
	punctuation; NEUTRAL		
	unidiomatic style; MINOR		
	punctuation; MINOR		
	grammar; NEUTRAL		
	grammar; NEUTRAL		
	textual conventions; MINOR		
	punctuation; MINOR		
	grammar; MINOR		
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	capitalisation; MINOR		
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	capitalisation; MINOR		
	grammar; MINOR		
	punctuation; MINOR		
	punctuation; MINOR		
	punctuation; MINOR		
	insertion; NEUTRAL		

	deletion; MINOR		
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<p>(capitalisation; MINOR) today we are (language register; NEUTRAL) going to see how to charge your electric or plug-in hybrid vehicle (punctuation; MINOR) (capitalisation; MINOR) in this case (punctuation; NEUTRAL) we are (language register; NEUTRAL) with an (grammar; MINOR) eniro (substitution; MAJOR) (punctuation; MINOR) (capitalisation; MINOR) it has the cover on the front (punctuation; MINOR) (capitalisation; MINOR) there are other vehicles that can (grammar; MINOR) have it on the front left (spelling; NEUTRAL) side or on the rear (omission; MINOR) side (punctuation; MINOR) (capitalisation; MINOR) in the open car (grammar; MINOR) (punctuation; MINOR) we will have to open the front portal (wrong term; MINOR) (punctuation; MINOR) (capitalisation; MINOR) we will find (awkward style; NEUTRAL) both the slow and fast charge (punctuation; MINOR) (capitalisation; MINOR) the slow one (awkward style; MINOR) will only be one of the holes (wrong term; MINOR) and the fast charge (awkward style; MINOR) (punctuation; MINOR) both holes (wrong term; MINOR) (punctuation; MINOR) (capitalisation; MINOR) you will have to go to (grammar; NEUTRAL) a charger (punctuation; MINOR) (capitalisation; MINOR) there will be free chargers (punctuation; MINOR) to which I will directly connect (substitution; MINOR) your charger and the charge (unidiomatic style; MINOR) will start (punctuation; MINOR) or there will be (awkward style; NEUTRAL) paid chargers (punctuation; NEUTRAL) which you will have (textual conventions; MINOR) to use the platform or card that the charger requires (punctuation; MINOR) (capitalisation; MINOR) you must take it (punctuation; MINOR) insert it (punctuation; NEUTRAL) and close the vehicle (punctuation; MINOR) I will hear (substitution; MINOR) a small flac (substitution; MINOR) that (grammar; NEUTRAL) will confirm that the charge (grammar; NEUTRAL) has started (punctuation; MINOR) (capitalisation; MINOR) you will be able to see in the front lights that the charge starts (unidiomatic style; MINOR) (punctuation; NEUTRAL) as you will see that they go up little by little (punctuation; NEUTRAL) and also on the interior infotainment screen (punctuation; MINOR) [Music] (insertion; NEUTRAL) (deletion; MINOR)</p>	<p>capitalisation; MINOR</p>	<p>capitalisation; MINOR</p>	<p>11</p>
<p>language register; NEUTRAL</p>	<p>language register; NEUTRAL</p>	<p>language register; NEUTRAL</p>	<p>2</p>
<p>punctuation; MINOR</p>	<p>punctuation; MINOR</p>	<p>punctuation; MINOR</p>	<p>17</p>
<p>capitalisation; MINOR</p>	<p>punctuation; NEUTRAL</p>	<p>punctuation; NEUTRAL</p>	<p>5</p>
<p>punctuation; NEUTRAL</p>	<p>grammar; MINOR</p>	<p>grammar; MINOR</p>	<p>3</p>
<p>language register; NEUTRAL</p>	<p>substitution; MAJOR</p>	<p>substitution; MAJOR</p>	<p>1</p>
<p>grammar; MINOR</p>	<p>spelling; NEUTRAL</p>	<p>spelling; NEUTRAL</p>	<p>1</p>
<p>substitution; MAJOR</p>	<p>omission; MINOR</p>	<p>omission; MINOR</p>	<p>1</p>
<p>punctuation; MINOR</p>	<p>wrong term; MINOR</p>	<p>wrong term; MINOR</p>	<p>3</p>
<p>capitalisation; MINOR</p>	<p>awkward style; NEUTRAL</p>	<p>awkward style; NEUTRAL</p>	<p>2</p>
<p>punctuation; MINOR</p>	<p>awkward style; MINOR</p>	<p>awkward style; MINOR</p>	<p>2</p>
<p>capitalisation; MINOR</p>	<p>grammar; NEUTRAL</p>	<p>grammar; NEUTRAL</p>	<p>3</p>
<p>grammar; MINOR</p>	<p>substitution; MINOR</p>	<p>substitution; MINOR</p>	<p>3</p>
<p>spelling; NEUTRAL</p>	<p>unidiomatic style; MINOR</p>	<p>unidiomatic style; MINOR</p>	<p>2</p>
<p>omission; MINOR</p>	<p>textual conventions; MINOR</p>	<p>textual conventions; MINOR</p>	<p>1</p>
<p>punctuation; MINOR</p>	<p>insertion; NEUTRAL</p>	<p>insertion; NEUTRAL</p>	<p>1</p>
<p>capitalisation; MINOR</p>	<p>deletion; MINOR</p>	<p>deletion; MINOR</p>	<p>1</p>
<p>grammar; MINOR</p>	<p></p>	<p></p>	<p></p>
<p>punctuation; MINOR</p>	<p></p>	<p></p>	<p></p>
<p>wrong term; MINOR</p>	<p></p>	<p></p>	<p></p>
<p>punctuation; MINOR</p>	<p></p>	<p></p>	<p></p>
<p>capitalisation; MINOR</p>	<p></p>	<p></p>	<p></p>
<p>awkward style; NEUTRAL</p>	<p></p>	<p></p>	<p></p>
<p>punctuation; MINOR</p>	<p></p>	<p></p>	<p></p>

	capitalisation; MINOR		
	awkward style; MINOR		
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	punctuation; MINOR		
	wrong term; MINOR		
	punctuation; MINOR		
	capitalisation; MINOR		
	grammar; NEUTRAL		
	punctuation; MINOR		
	capitalisation; MINOR		
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	unidiomatic style; MINOR		
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	awkward style; NEUTRAL		
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	punctuation; MINOR		
	capitalisation; MINOR		
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	punctuation; NEUTRAL		
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	punctuation; MINOR		
	insertion; NEUTRAL		
	deletion; MINOR		

<p>Hello (punctuation; MINOR) hello (punctuation; MINOR) in (capitalisation; MINOR) this howu (substitution; MINOR) (punctuation; NEUTRAL) we are going to explain what to do if the solar remote control of your TV (awkward style; MINOR) does not respond (grammar; MINOR). We begin by first having to (grammar; MINOR) check if the remote control is charged and connected by Bluetooth to the TV (grammar; MINOR), (punctuation; MINOR) (substitution; MINOR) such as (punctuation; MINOR) (capitalisation; MINOR) standing near (grammar; MINOR) the TV and simultaneously (grammar; NEUTRAL) pressing the return (capitalisation; MINOR) (grammar; MINOR) Play (substitution; MINOR) buttons for a few seconds (punctuation; MINOR) (capitalisation; MINOR) the TV should pair with the remote control and show (grammar; NEUTRAL) the battery charge status, (punctuation; MINOR) (capitalisation; MINOR) otherwise (grammar; NEUTRAL) if it does not (language register; NEUTRAL) pair or is discharged (mistranslation; MINOR). (punctuation; MINOR) Remember (capitalisation; MINOR) that you can charge it with indoor or outdoor light (punctuation; MINOR) with a USB type C charger (punctuation; MINOR) like the one on (grammar; MINOR) your mobile phone (punctuation; MINOR) or by absorbing RF waves (punctuation; MINOR) like those of the (grammar; MINOR) router (punctuation; MINOR) that (grammar; MINOR) transforms them into energy (mistranslation; MINOR) (grammar; MINOR) and charges it (grammar; MINOR). I hope this info has gotten you out of trouble (awkward style; NEUTRAL) (punctuation; NEUTRAL) See (capitalisation; NEUTRAL) you in a next howu (substitution; MINOR) (punctuation; MINOR)</p>	<p>punctuation; MINOR</p>	<p>punctuation; MINOR</p>	<p>13</p>
<p></p>	<p>punctuation; MINOR</p>	<p>capitalisation; MINOR</p>	<p>6</p>
<p></p>	<p>capitalisation; MINOR</p>	<p>substitution; MINOR</p>	<p>4</p>
<p></p>	<p>substitution; MINOR</p>	<p>punctuation; NEUTRAL</p>	<p>2</p>
<p></p>	<p>punctuation; NEUTRAL</p>	<p>awkward style; MINOR</p>	<p>1</p>
<p></p>	<p>awkward style; MINOR</p>	<p>grammar; MINOR</p>	<p>10</p>
<p></p>	<p>grammar; MINOR</p>	<p>grammar; NEUTRAL</p>	<p>3</p>
<p></p>	<p>grammar; MINOR</p>	<p>language register; NEUTRAL</p>	<p>1</p>
<p></p>	<p>grammar; MINOR</p>	<p>mistranslation; MINOR</p>	<p>2</p>
<p></p>	<p>punctuation; MINOR</p>	<p>awkward style; NEUTRAL</p>	<p>1</p>
<p></p>	<p>substitution; MINOR</p>	<p>capitalisation; NEUTRAL</p>	<p>1</p>
<p></p>	<p>punctuation; MINOR</p>	<p></p>	<p></p>
<p></p>	<p>capitalisation; MINOR</p>	<p></p>	<p></p>
<p></p>	<p>grammar; MINOR</p>	<p></p>	<p></p>
<p></p>	<p>grammar; NEUTRAL</p>	<p></p>	<p></p>
<p></p>	<p>capitalisation; MINOR</p>	<p></p>	<p></p>
<p></p>	<p>grammar; MINOR</p>	<p></p>	<p></p>
<p></p>	<p>substitution; MINOR</p>	<p></p>	<p></p>
<p></p>	<p>punctuation; MINOR</p>	<p></p>	<p></p>
<p></p>	<p>capitalisation; MINOR</p>	<p></p>	<p></p>
<p></p>	<p>grammar; NEUTRAL</p>	<p></p>	<p></p>
<p></p>	<p>punctuation; MINOR</p>	<p></p>	<p></p>
<p></p>	<p>capitalisation; MINOR</p>	<p></p>	<p></p>
<p></p>	<p>grammar; NEUTRAL</p>	<p></p>	<p></p>
<p></p>	<p>language register; NEUTRAL</p>	<p></p>	<p></p>
<p></p>	<p>mistranslation; MINOR</p>	<p></p>	<p></p>
<p></p>	<p>punctuation; MINOR</p>	<p></p>	<p></p>
<p></p>	<p>capitalisation; MINOR</p>	<p></p>	<p></p>

	punctuation; MINOR		
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	punctuation; MINOR		
	grammar; MINOR		
	mistranslation; MINOR		
	grammar; MINOR		
	grammar; MINOR		
	awkward style; NEUTRAL		
	punctuation; NEUTRAL		
	capitalisation; NEUTRAL		
	substitution; MINOR		
	punctuation; MINOR		

<p>Hello (punctuation; MINOR) hello (punctuation; MINOR) (capitalisation; MINOR) today I am going to teach (language register; MINOR) you (capitalisation; MINOR) How to update the software on your TV (language register; NEUTRAL) with a USB from the Samsung website (punctuation; MINOR) The first thing you will (language register; NEUTRAL) have to do is select the menu, (punctuation; MINOR)(capitalisation; MINOR) (grammar; MINOR) select (capitalisation; MINOR) settings, (capitalisation; MINOR)support and select (awkward style; NEUTRAL) (capitalisation; MINOR)about this TV, (punctuation; MINOR)(capitalisation; MINOR) check (mistranslation; MINOR) the code of your TV and the software version. Remember these details as they will be very important (capitalisation; MINOR)When you go to the Samsung website and download the latest version of your TV's software,(punctuation; MINOR) (capitalisation; MINOR) unzip the file and save it in the top-level (unidiomatic style; MINOR) folder of the USB drive connected to your PC.(punctuation; MINOR) (capitalisation; MINOR) follow these steps (punctuation; NEUTRAL) because otherwise the TV will not be able to locate the update package (punctuation; MINOR) (capitalisation; MINOR) insert the external USB drive into the slot designed (grammar; NEUTRAL) for these devices on the TV. Once you have completed these steps (punctuation; NEUTRAL) you will have to go to settings (capitalisation; MINOR), support (inconsistent with terminology resource; MINOR) software update (capitalisation; MINOR) (punctuation; NEUTRAL) and update (capitalisation; MINOR) now, (punctuation; MINOR) (capitalisation; MINOR) important (punctuation; MINOR) (capitalisation; MINOR) do not turn off the TV or remove the USB drive until the update is complete. (capitalisation; MINOR) ready(punctuation; MINOR)</p>	<p>punctuation; MINOR</p>	<p>punctuation; MINOR</p>	<p>11</p>
	<p>punctuation; MINOR</p>	<p>capitalisation; MINOR</p>	<p>17</p>
	<p>capitalisation; MINOR</p>	<p>language register; MINOR</p>	<p>1</p>
	<p>language register; MINOR</p>	<p>language register; NEUTRAL</p>	<p>2</p>
	<p>capitalisation; MINOR</p>	<p>grammar; MINOR</p>	<p>1</p>
	<p>language register; NEUTRAL</p>	<p>awkward style; NEUTRAL</p>	<p>1</p>
	<p>punctuation; MINOR</p>	<p>mistranslation; MINOR</p>	<p>1</p>
	<p>language register; NEUTRAL</p>	<p>unidiomatic style; MINOR</p>	<p>1</p>
	<p>punctuation; MINOR</p>	<p>punctuation; NEUTRAL</p>	<p>3</p>
	<p>capitalisation; MINOR</p>	<p>grammar; NEUTRAL</p>	<p>1</p>
	<p>grammar; MINOR</p>	<p>inconsistent with terminology reso</p>	<p>1</p>
	<p>capitalisation; MINOR</p>		
	<p>capitalisation; MINOR</p>		
	<p>awkward style; NEUTRAL</p>		
	<p>capitalisation; MINOR</p>		
	<p>punctuation; MINOR</p>		
	<p>capitalisation; MINOR</p>		
	<p>mistranslation; MINOR</p>		
	<p>capitalisation; MINOR</p>		
	<p>punctuation; MINOR</p>		
	<p>capitalisation; MINOR</p>		
	<p>unidiomatic style; MINOR</p>		
	<p>punctuation; MINOR</p>		
	<p>capitalisation; MINOR</p>		
	<p>punctuation; NEUTRAL</p>		
	<p>punctuation; MINOR</p>		
	<p>capitalisation; MINOR</p>		

	grammar; NEUTRAL		
	punctuation; NEUTRAL		
	capitalisation; MINOR		
	inconsistent with terminology resource; MINOR		
	capitalisation; MINOR		
	punctuation; NEUTRAL		
	capitalisation; MINOR		
	punctuation; MINOR		
	capitalisation; MINOR		
	punctuation; MINOR		
	capitalisation; MINOR		
	capitalisation; MINOR		
	punctuation; MINOR		

<p>Hello (punctuation; MINOR) hello (punctuation; MINOR) (capitalisation; MINOR) today we are going to discuss (language register; NEUTRAL) the benefits of having a television (language register; MINOR) with artificial intelligence (punctuation; MINOR) (capitalisation; MINOR) we start with (grammar; MINOR) (capitalisation; MINOR) the new processors of Samsung televisions (awkward style; MINOR) with artificial intelligence identifies (substitution; MINOR) our consumption (language register; NEUTRAL) habits to adapt to what we see (mistranslation; MINOR) and improve (grammar; NEUTRAL) quality (punctuation; MINOR) (capitalisation; MINOR) (grammar; MINOR) not only corrects defects (punctuation; NEUTRAL) but it is a learning process by which it improves (grammar; NEUTRAL) image and sound (punctuation; MINOR) (capitalisation; MINOR) how do I benefit from it (punctuation; MINOR) (capitalisation; MINOR) now (grammar; NEUTRAL) Samsung televisions make the appropriate (language register; MINOR) adjustments so that you can see (mistranslation; MINOR) your favourite sports more clearly (punctuation; MINOR) (capitalisation; MINOR) for example (punctuation; NEUTRAL) in a tennis match (punctuation; MINOR) it will offer better quality in the movement of the ball so that you do not (language register; MINOR) miss any detail (punctuation; MINOR) (capitalisation; MINOR) thanks to the Ai app scaling (substitution; MINOR) (punctuation; MINOR) even having less quality than the resolution of the television (language register; MINOR) (textual conventions; MINOR) (punctuation; MINOR) the television (language register; MINOR) will rescale (wrong term; MINOR) the content you are watching to 8k (inconsistent with external reference; NEUTRAL) (punctuation; MINOR) (capitalisation; MINOR) and no strange noises (punctuation; MINOR) (capitalisation; MINOR) the television (language register; MINOR) is responsible for (mistranslation; MINOR) improving the audio of a dialogue (awkward style; MINOR) without distorting the sound of the entire (grammar; NEUTRAL) scene (punctuation; MINOR) Ai (inconsistent with external reference; MINOR) Energy Mode (punctuation; MINOR) which is responsible for ensuring that the television (language register; MINOR) optimizes the lighting (wrong term; MINOR) according to the content we are watching (punctuation; MINOR) (capitalisation; MINOR) it is (language register; NEUTRAL) up to you to choose in which range (textual conventions; NEUTRAL) of televisions you are going to (language register; NEUTRAL) enjoy these incredible results (grammar; MINOR) (punctuation; MINOR) (capitalisation; MINOR) we are clear (mistranslation; MINOR) Neo (capitalisation; MINOR) cued (substitution; MAJOR) 8k (inconsistent with external reference; NEUTRAL) (punctuation; MINOR) because it has the most advanced processors (punctuation; MINOR)</p>	<p>punctuation; MINOR</p>	<p>punctuation; MINOR</p>	<p>19</p>
	punctuation; MINOR	capitalisation; MINOR	13
	capitalisation; MINOR	language register; NEUTRAL	4
	language register; NEUTRAL	language register; MINOR	7
	language register; MINOR	grammar; MINOR	3
	punctuation; MINOR	awkward style; MINOR	2
	capitalisation; MINOR	substitution; MINOR	2
	grammar; MINOR	mistranslation; MINOR	4
	capitalisation; MINOR	grammar; NEUTRAL	4
	awkward style; MINOR	punctuation; NEUTRAL	2
	substitution; MINOR	textual conventions; MINOR	1
	language register; NEUTRAL	wrong term; MINOR	2
	mistranslation; MINOR	inconsistent with external referenc	2
	grammar; NEUTRAL	inconsistent with external referenc	1
	punctuation; MINOR	textual conventions; NEUTRAL	1
	capitalisation; MINOR	substitution; MAJOR	1
	grammar; MINOR		
	punctuation; NEUTRAL		
	grammar; NEUTRAL		
	punctuation; MINOR		

	capitalisation; MINOR		
	punctuation; MINOR		
	capitalisation; MINOR		
	grammar; NEUTRAL		
	language register; MINOR		
	mistranslation; MINOR		
	punctuation; MINOR		
	capitalisation; MINOR		
	punctuation; NEUTRAL		
	punctuation; MINOR		
	language register; MINOR		
	punctuation; MINOR		
	capitalisation; MINOR		
	substitution; MINOR		
	punctuation; MINOR		
	language register; MINOR		
	textual conventions; MINOR		
	punctuation; MINOR		
	language register; MINOR		
	wrong term; MINOR		
	inconsistent with external reference; NEUTRAL		
	punctuation; MINOR		
	capitalisation; MINOR		
	punctuation; MINOR		
	capitalisation; MINOR		
	language register; MINOR		
	mistranslation; MINOR		
	awkward style; MINOR		
	grammar; NEUTRAL		
	punctuation; MINOR		
	inconsistent with external reference; MINOR		
	punctuation; MINOR		
	language register; MINOR		
	wrong term; MINOR		
	punctuation; MINOR		
	capitalisation; MINOR		

	language register; NEUTRAL		
	textual conventions; NEUTRAL		
	language register; NEUTRAL		
	grammar; MINOR		
	punctuation; MINOR		
	capitalisation; MINOR		
	mistranslation; MINOR		
	capitalisation; MINOR		
	substitution; MAJOR		
	inconsistent with external reference; NEUTRAL		
	punctuation; MINOR		
	punctuation; MINOR		

<p>Hello (punctuation; MINOR) (capitalisation; MINOR) hello(punctuation; MINOR) (capitalisation; MINOR) in this How (capitalisation; MINOR) to I am going to teach you (awkward style; MINOR) (capitalisation; MINOR) How to add your Samsung TV to the smarthing (substitution; MINOR) app to control the smart devices in your home. It is (language register; NEUTRAL) compatible with a lot of (language register; NEUTRAL) brands (punctuation; NEUTRAL) in addition to (language register; NEUTRAL) the virtual assistants of (awkward style; MINOR) Samsung, Google, and Amazon. And to add your smartthings (substitution; MINOR) TV (mistranslation; MINOR) (punctuation; MINOR) you can do it through automatic or manual registration (textual conventions; NEUTRAL), but remember it always has to be (grammar; NEUTRAL) connected to the internet. For automatic registration, activate the application (language register; MINOR) and log in with your Samsung account. You will see how it detects the Smart TVs nearby (substitution; NEUTRAL) and a registration pop-up window will appear. When you see that (punctuation; MINOR) it asks you to Add the TV, press Add. (punctuation; MINOR) (capitalisation; MINOR) Now press start (wrong term; MINOR) and select (capitalisation; MINOR) location and room. Now (punctuation; NEUTRAL) if the smarthing (substitution; MINOR) app does not detect your TV automatically, you can register it manually. Turn on your TV and start the smarthing (substitution; MINOR) application (language register; MINOR). Once inside, select TV, enter (grammar; NEUTRAL) the pin (substitution; MINOR) that appears on the TV screen and wait for the process to complete and that would be all (language register; MINOR). See you in the next howto. (substitution; MINOR)</p>	<p>punctuation; MINOR</p>		
	capitalisation; MINOR	punctuation; MINOR	5
	punctuation; MINOR	capitalisation; MINOR	6
	capitalisation; MINOR	awkward style; MINOR	2
	capitalisation; MINOR	substitution; MINOR	6
	capitalisation; MINOR	language register; NEUTRAL	3
	awkward style; MINOR	punctuation; NEUTRAL	2
	capitalisation; MINOR	mistranslation; MINOR	1
	substitution; MINOR	textual conventions; NEUTRAL	1
	language register; NEUTRAL	grammar; NEUTRAL	2
	language register; NEUTRAL	language register; MINOR	3
	punctuation; NEUTRAL	substitution; NEUTRAL	1
	language register; NEUTRAL	wrong term; MINOR	1
	awkward style; MINOR		
	substitution; MINOR		
	mistranslation; MINOR		
	punctuation; MINOR		
	textual conventions; NEUTRAL		
	grammar; NEUTRAL		
	language register; MINOR		
	substitution; NEUTRAL		
	punctuation; MINOR		
	punctuation; MINOR		
	capitalisation; MINOR		
	wrong term; MINOR		
	capitalisation; MINOR		
	punctuation; NEUTRAL		
	substitution; MINOR		

	substitution; MINOR		
	language register; MINOR		
	grammar; NEUTRAL		
	substitution; MINOR		
	language register; MINOR		
	substitution; MINOR		

<p>[Music] (insertion; NEUTRAL) Every step I take (awkward style; MINOR) and every stride I make (grammar; NEUTRAL) is always filled with a purpose (punctuation; MINOR) and (grammar; MINOR) a goal (punctuation; NEUTRAL) and a dream that I want to achieve (punctuation; MINOR) in (capitalisation; MINOR) general(punctuation; NEUTRAL) in my day to day (spelling; NEUTRAL) (textual conventions; NEUTRAL) (punctuation; NEUTRAL) even if I'm not (omission; MINOR) I use meditation a lot (awkward style; MINOR) but then just before competing (punctuation; NEUTRAL) I need to (omission; NEUTRAL) concentrate and I would be (substitution; MINOR) isolated. For that, the Anis (substitution; MAJOR) app is great with the Galaxy bats (substitution; MAJOR) which are the best (unidiomatic style; NEUTRAL). With focus, with passion (punctuation; MINOR) you can achieve things you never thought possible. (awkward style; NEUTRAL)</p>	<p>insertion; NEUTRAL</p>	<p>insertion; NEUTRAL</p>	<p>1</p>
	awkward style; MINOR	awkward style; MINOR	2
	grammar; NEUTRAL	grammar; NEUTRAL	1
	punctuation; MINOR	punctuation; MINOR	3
	grammar; MINOR	grammar; MINOR	1
	punctuation; NEUTRAL	punctuation; NEUTRAL	4
	punctuation; MINOR	capitalisation; MINOR	1
	capitalisation; MINOR	spelling; NEUTRAL	1
	punctuation; NEUTRAL	textual conventions; NEUTRAL	1
	spelling; NEUTRAL	omission; MINOR	1
	textual conventions; NEUTRAL	omission; NEUTRAL	1
	punctuation; NEUTRAL	substitution; MINOR	1
	omission; MINOR	substitution; MAJOR	2
	awkward style; MINOR	unidiomatic style; NEUTRAL	1
	punctuation; NEUTRAL	awkward style; NEUTRAL	1
	omission; NEUTRAL		
	substitution; MINOR		
	substitution; MAJOR		
	substitution; MAJOR		
	unidiomatic style; NEUTRAL		
	punctuation; MINOR		
	awkward style; NEUTRAL		

<p>[Music] (insertion; NEUTRAL) Who doesn't like to save a little money at IKEA? I'll tell you (unidiomatic style; MINOR). (punctuation; NEUTRAL) We've (capitalisation; NEUTRAL) launched the (grammar; NEUTRAL) new rewards for IKEA family (capitalisation; MINOR), which are the new advantages for (grammar; NEUTRAL) the club. Until now (punctuation; NEUTRAL) they (grammar; MINOR) had exclusive advantages, discounts, and the famous free coffees. Now you can accumulate points and spend them on whatever you want:(punctuation; NEUTRAL) on services, in restaurants (grammar; MINOR), on products, (punctuation; NEUTRAL) on (grammar; NEUTRAL) anything within (capitalisation; MINOR) Ikea. For example, for a purchase of 5 euros you get one point, (awkward style; NEUTRAL) (punctuation; MINOR) but you can also accumulate points for many other things, such as (grammar; NEUTRAL) logging into the website, creating a wishlist, coming to an event in the store (awkward style; NEUTRAL), among other things (punctuation; MINOR) (capitalisation; NEUTRAL) and then you take your points and spend them on whatever you want. For example, with 50 points you unlock a coupon for 5 (deletion; MINOR) for your next home delivery. Well, if you're not a member yet, you can go to the website, create an account really quickly (unidiomatic style; MINOR) and for free, and accumulate points. Bye. (punctuation; NEUTRAL)</p>	<p>insertion; NEUTRAL</p>	<p>insertion; NEUTRAL</p>	<p>1</p>
	<p>unidiomatic style; MINOR</p>	<p>unidiomatic style; MINOR</p>	<p>2</p>
	<p>punctuation; NEUTRAL</p>	<p>punctuation; NEUTRAL</p>	<p>5</p>
	<p>capitalisation; NEUTRAL</p>	<p>capitalisation; NEUTRAL</p>	<p>2</p>
	<p>grammar; NEUTRAL</p>	<p>grammar; NEUTRAL</p>	<p>4</p>
	<p>capitalisation; MINOR</p>	<p>capitalisation; MINOR</p>	<p>2</p>
	<p>grammar; NEUTRAL</p>	<p>grammar; MINOR</p>	<p>2</p>
	<p>punctuation; NEUTRAL</p>	<p>awkward style; NEUTRAL</p>	<p>2</p>
	<p>grammar; MINOR</p>	<p>punctuation; MINOR</p>	<p>2</p>
	<p>punctuation; NEUTRAL</p>	<p>deletion; MINOR</p>	<p>1</p>
	<p>grammar; MINOR</p>		
	<p>punctuation; NEUTRAL</p>		
	<p>grammar; NEUTRAL</p>		
	<p>capitalisation; MINOR</p>		
	<p>awkward style; NEUTRAL</p>		
	<p>punctuation; MINOR</p>		
	<p>grammar; NEUTRAL</p>		
	<p>awkward style; NEUTRAL</p>		
	<p>punctuation; MINOR</p>		
	<p>capitalisation; NEUTRAL</p>		
	<p>deletion; MINOR</p>		
	<p>unidiomatic style; MINOR</p>		
	<p>punctuation; NEUTRAL</p>		

<p>(capitalisation; MINOR) when you come to IKEA to choose a new mattress (punctuation; MINOR) you always ask us what it should be like, (punctuation; NEUTRAL) (capitalisation; NEUTRAL) well (punctuation; NEUTRAL) today I'm going to tell you (punctuation; MINOR) (capitalisation; MINOR) the first thing you need to know is if (grammar; NEUTRAL) you're going to sleep alone or with someone (grammar; NEUTRAL). If you sleep as a couple and one of you moves a lot because you can't sleep, a pocket spring mattress (inconsistent with terminology resource; NEUTRAL) is the best option, and if you like to sleep snuggled up without moving much, a memory foam mattress will hug you all night long. The second thing is to choose the firmness of the mattress. If you always sleep on your back or on your (awkward style; NEUTRAL) side and if you (awkward style; NEUTRAL) weigh more than 85 kg, we recommend choosing an extra firm mattress. (punctuation; MINOR) (capitalisation; MINOR) If you sleep on your stomach or on your (awkward style; NEUTRAL) side and you (awkward style; NEUTRAL) weigh less than 85 kg, the best option is to choose a mattress with a lower firmness (unidiomatic style; MINOR) that adapts to your body. Finally, choose the size of the mattress (awkward style; NEUTRAL) well (punctuation; NEUTRAL) and don't forget to choose your perfect pillow so that your dreams don't end before their time. (awkward style; MINOR)</p>	<p>capitalisation; MINOR</p>		
		<p>capitalisation; MINOR</p>	<p>3</p>
	<p>punctuation; MINOR</p>	<p>punctuation; MINOR</p>	<p>3</p>
	<p>punctuation; NEUTRAL</p>	<p>punctuation; NEUTRAL</p>	<p>3</p>
	<p>capitalisation; NEUTRAL</p>	<p>capitalisation; NEUTRAL</p>	<p>1</p>
	<p>punctuation; NEUTRAL</p>	<p>grammar; NEUTRAL</p>	<p>2</p>
	<p>punctuation; MINOR</p>	<p>inconsistent with terminology reso</p>	<p>1</p>
	<p>capitalisation; MINOR</p>	<p>awkward style; NEUTRAL</p>	<p>5</p>
	<p>grammar; NEUTRAL</p>	<p>unidiomatic style; MINOR</p>	<p>1</p>
	<p>grammar; NEUTRAL</p>	<p>awkward style; MINOR</p>	<p>1</p>
	<p>inconsistent with terminology resource; NEUTRAL</p>		
	<p>awkward style; NEUTRAL</p>		
	<p>awkward style; NEUTRAL</p>		
	<p>punctuation; MINOR</p>		
	<p>capitalisation; MINOR</p>		
	<p>awkward style; NEUTRAL</p>		
	<p>awkward style; NEUTRAL</p>		
	<p>unidiomatic style; MINOR</p>		
	<p>awkward style; NEUTRAL</p>		
	<p>punctuation; NEUTRAL</p>		
	<p>awkward style; MINOR</p>		

<p>If you haven't checked (mistranslation; MINOR) your pillow lately because it's a little old, it's because you haven't given it all the love it deserved. The most important thing for a pillow to last a long time is that the filling, in addition to (awkward style; NEUTRAL) being comfortable, is breathable and absorbs moisture. As a second piece of advice (awkward style; NEUTRAL), before putting on the sheet set's cover (grammar; MINOR), always use protective pillowcases. You can use a basic one like this one or a thermal one that, depending on the color of each side, gives you cooler sleep in the summer or warmer sleep in the winter (unidiomatic style; MINOR)</p>	mistranslation; MINOR		
		mistranslation; MINOR	1
	awkward style; NEUTRAL	awkward style; NEUTRAL	2
	awkward style; NEUTRAL	grammar; MINOR	1
	grammar; MINOR	unidiomatic style; MINOR	1
	unidiomatic style; MINOR		

<p>You too, when you finish a coffee, you're already thinking about the next one (unidiomatic style; NEUTRAL) (punctuation; MINOR) Well, (grammar; MINOR) come on up and set up a coffee corner with my favorite products. It's not coming up too high (mistranslation; MINOR), and it's not a coffee corner if you don't have a really cool organizer that serves as a canvas for everything else. You need a coffee maker, and if you also have a mat (mistranslation; MINOR), even better. You also need some aetic (substitution; MINOR) jars. And if you like coffee, have (undertranslation; MINOR) two cups, or three or four. Now place (grammar; MINOR) a (omission; NEUTRAL) jug for the milk (punctuation; NEUTRAL) and the spoons (undertranslation; NEUTRAL), and to finish, an aromatic (substitution; MINOR) candle.(punctuation; MINOR) You (capitalisation; MINOR) already have unidiomatic style; MINOR) your coffee corner. (punctuation; NEUTRAL) Now it's your turn to come up even higher (mistranslation; MINOR) and share it on your social networks. Bye. (punctuation; NEUTRAL)</p>	<p>unidiomatic style; NEUTRAL</p>	<p>unidiomatic style; NEUTRAL</p>	<p>1</p>
	punctuation; MINOR	punctuation; MINOR	2
	grammar; MINOR	grammar; MINOR	2
	mistranslation; MINOR	mistranslation; MINOR	3
	mistranslation; MINOR	substitution; MINOR	2
	substitution; MINOR	undertranslation; MINOR	1
	undertranslation; MINOR	omission; NEUTRAL	1
	grammar; MINOR	punctuation; NEUTRAL	3
	omission; NEUTRAL	undertranslation; NEUTRAL	1
	punctuation; NEUTRAL	capitalisation; MINOR	1
	undertranslation; NEUTRAL		
	substitution; MINOR		
	punctuation; MINOR		
	capitalisation; MINOR		
	punctuation; NEUTRAL		
	mistranslation; MINOR		
	punctuation; NEUTRAL		

<p>(textual conventions; NEUTRAL) You want to win the award for mother or father of the year by making your little one enjoy playing in their room (punctuation; MINOR) Then you have to go from this to this (punctuation; MINOR) The first thing is to (awkward style; NEUTRAL) choose an area that does not (language register; NEUTRAL) interrupt the passage (unidiomatic style; MINOR) and avoid (grammar; MINOR) problems (punctuation; MINOR) I have (language register; NEUTRAL) chosen this one (punctuation; MINOR) Now it is (language register; NEUTRAL) time to choose a fun rug so that (grammar; NEUTRAL) the little ones are comfortable and warm (punctuation; MINOR) Add seating areas full of color (awkward style; NEUTRAL) (punctuation; NEUTRAL) with some fun cushions is enough (grammar; MINOR) (punctuation; MINOR) Now comes the fauna (language register; MINOR) (punctuation; MINOR) Add all the stuffed animals that you consider (unidiomatic style; MINOR) (punctuation; MINOR) It is (language register; MINOR) good for the little ones to become familiar with the (grammar; MINOR) different animals (punctuation; MINOR) (capitalisation; MINOR) and for them to develop their most creative side (punctuation; MINOR) (capitalisation; MINOR) An easel for them to paint, draw (punctuation; NEUTRAL) or express themselves in their own way (punctuation; MINOR) (capitalisation; MINOR) and well playing is very good (unidiomatic style; MINOR) (punctuation; MINOR) but they also have to learn to clean up (punctuation; MINOR) (capitalisation; MINOR) So a good (punctuation; MINOR) light (punctuation; NEUTRAL) and accessible box is perfect for them to do it themselves (punctuation; MINOR) Now it is (language register; MINOR) your turn to enjoy time with them in their play area (punctuation; MINOR) (omission; MINOR) for the prize (punctuation; MINOR)</p>	<p>textual conventions; NEUTRAL</p>	<p>textual conventions; NEUTRAL</p>	<p>1</p>
	<p>punctuation; MINOR</p>	<p>punctuation; MINOR</p>	<p>17</p>
	<p>punctuation; MINOR</p>	<p>awkward style; NEUTRAL</p>	<p>2</p>
	<p>awkward style; NEUTRAL</p>	<p>language register; NEUTRAL</p>	<p>3</p>
	<p>language register; NEUTRAL</p>	<p>unidiomatic style; MINOR</p>	<p>3</p>
	<p>unidiomatic style; MINOR</p>	<p>grammar; MINOR</p>	<p>3</p>
	<p>grammar; MINOR</p>	<p>grammar; NEUTRAL</p>	<p>1</p>
	<p>punctuation; MINOR</p>	<p>punctuation; NEUTRAL</p>	<p>3</p>
	<p>language register; NEUTRAL</p>	<p>language register; MINOR</p>	<p>3</p>
	<p>punctuation; MINOR</p>	<p>capitalisation; MINOR</p>	<p>4</p>
	<p>language register; NEUTRAL</p>	<p>omission; MINOR</p>	<p>1</p>
	<p>grammar; NEUTRAL</p>		
	<p>punctuation; MINOR</p>		
	<p>awkward style; NEUTRAL</p>		
	<p>punctuation; NEUTRAL</p>		
	<p>grammar; MINOR</p>		
	<p>punctuation; MINOR</p>		
	<p>language register; MINOR</p>		
	<p>punctuation; MINOR</p>		
	<p>unidiomatic style; MINOR</p>		
	<p>punctuation; MINOR</p>		
	<p>language register; MINOR</p>		
	<p>grammar; MINOR</p>		
	<p>punctuation; MINOR</p>		
	<p>capitalisation; MINOR</p>		
	<p>punctuation; MINOR</p>		

	capitalisation; MINOR		
	punctuation; NEUTRAL		
	punctuation; MINOR		
	capitalisation; MINOR		
	unidiomatic style; MINOR		
	punctuation; MINOR		
	punctuation; MINOR		
	capitalisation; MINOR		
	punctuation; MINOR		
	punctuation; NEUTRAL		
	punctuation; MINOR		
	language register; MINOR		
	punctuation; MINOR		
	omission; MINOR		
	punctuation; MINOR		

